

New records of longhorn beetles (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae) in Bulgaria

Denis Gradinarov¹, Ognyan Sivilov¹, Victor Gashtarov², Enrico Migliaccio³,
Vladimir Sakalian⁴, Georgi Georgiev⁵

¹ Faculty of Biology, Sofia University St. Kliment Ohridski, 8 Dragan Tzankov Blvd., 1164 Sofia, Bulgaria

² Private entomologist, P.O. Box 470, 1000 Sofia, Bulgaria

³ Science Naturali ed Ambientali, 47 Via Duccio Galimberti, 00136 Roma, Italy

⁴ Institute of Biodiversity and Ecosystem Research, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, 2 Gagarin Str., 1113 Sofia, Bulgaria

⁵ Forest Research Institute, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, 132, St. Kliment Ohridski Blvd., 1756 Sofia, Bulgaria

Corresponding author: Georgi Georgiev (ggeorgiev.fri@gmail.com)

Academic editor: M. Georgieva | Received 10 March 2020 | Accepted 12 April 2020 | Published 30 June 2020

Citation: Gradinarov D., O. Sivilov, V. Gashtarov, E. Migliaccio, V. Sakalian, G. Georgiev (2020) New records of longhorn beetles (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae) in Bulgaria. *Silva Balcanica* 21(1): 91–112. <https://doi.org/10.3897/silvabalcanica.21.e54609>

Abstract

During the period 1969–2019, longhorn beetles (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae) were studied in Bulgaria. In different regions of the country, 144 cerambycid taxa from six subfamilies were established: Prioniinae (five species), Lepturinae (37 species and subspecies), Necydalinae (one species), Spondylidinae (nine species and subspecies), Cerambycinae (46 species and subspecies) and Lamiinae (46 species and subspecies). New localities of 14 rare cerambycid taxa were established (*Pedostrangalia revestita*, *Alocerus moesiacus*, *Anisarthron barbipes*, *Icosium tomentosum atticum*, *Paraclytus sexguttatus*, *Aegomorphus krueperi*, *Agapanthia frivaldszkyi*, *Deroplia genei genei*, *Dorcadion equestre transsilvanicum*, *Phytoecia albovittigera*, *Phytoecia praetextata praetextata*, *Pogonocherus hispidus*, *Niphona picticornis* and *Saperda perforata*). New longhorn beetles were also found in the West Balkan Range, the Eastern and Western Rhodopes, Maleshevska Planina Mt. and North-eastern Bulgaria. These new records enlarged the knowledge about the regional distribution of longhorn beetles in Bulgaria.

Keywords

Cerambycidae, distribution, rare species, Bulgaria

Introduction

The longhorn beetles (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae) are relatively well studied in Bulgaria. At present, over 260 cerambycid taxa have been established and reported in the country (Georgiev, Hubenov, 2006; Migliaccio et al., 2007; Danilevsky et al., 2016; etc.). It could be noted, however, that there is still insufficient knowledge about species distribution in different regions of Bulgaria.

This paper reports data about new records and localities of longhorn beetles in Bulgaria.

Material and methods

The studies were conducted during the period 1969 – 2019, using two classical entomological methods: (i) hand collection of cerambycids on flowers and host plants; (ii) collection of adult insects on grass, bushes and low parts of trees with entomological bag.

The longhorn beetles are listed in systematic order, following the system of Danilevsky (2019).

The biological material is deposited in entomological collections mentioned with the following abbreviations: [BFUS] – Zoological Collection of Sofia University ‘St. Kliment Ohridski’, Faculty of Biology, Sofia, Bulgaria; [EM] – entomological collection of Enrico Migliaccio; [GG] – entomological collection of Georgi Georgiev; [VG] – entomological collection of Victor Gashtarov.

Results and Discussion

In this study, 144 cerambycid taxa from six subfamilies were established: Prioninae (five species), Lepturinae (37 species and subspecies), Necydalinae (one species), Spondylidinae (nine species and subspecies), Cerambycinae (46 species and subspecies) and Lamiinae (46 species and subspecies).

PRIONINAE

Aegosoma scabricorne (Scopoli, 1763)

Black Sea Coast: S of Kranevo, Zlatni Pyasatsi Nature Park, 43°20'02.97"N, 28°03'37.19"E, 160 m a.s.l., 24.07.2011, 1 ♀, at light, O. Sivilov & B. Zlatkov leg. [BFUS]. **Pirin Mt.:** 3.5 km NE of Kalimantsi Vill., right bank of Kalimanska Reka Riv., 41°27'59.70"N, 23°30'57.60"E, 387 m a.s.l., 12.08.2015, 1 ♂, 1 ♀, at light, Y. Petrova & B. Zlatkov leg. [BFUS]; 1 km NE of Kalimantsi Vill., road to Belyovo Vill., Sveti Ilia Hill, 41°27'54.30"N, 23°29'23.52"E, 320 m a.s.l., 31.07.2016, 1 ♂, at light, Y. Petrova & B. Zlatkov leg. [BFUS].

Ergates faber faber (Linnaeus, 1761)

Pirin Mt.: 600 m N of Nova Lovcha Vill., 41°25'35.34"N, 23°43'16.02"E, 780 m a.s.l., 13.08.2015, 1 ♀, at light, Y. Petrova & B. Zlatkov leg. [BFUS].

***Mesoprionus besikanus* (Fairmaire, 1855)**

Sredna Gora Mt.: Hysaria, 30.07.2001, 1 ex., L. Gramenova leg. [EM]. **Maleshvska Planina Mt.:** Mikrevo Vill., 260 m a.s.l., 02-30.07.2002, 2 ex., S. Lazarov and T. Ljubomirov leg. [EM]; 1 km SE of Kamenitsa Vill., 41°38'32.88"N, 23°09'59.04"E, 239 m a.s.l., 30.07.2016, 1 ♂, at light, Y. Petrova & B. Zlatkov leg. [BFUS].

***Prionus coriarius* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

The Western Rhodopes: Kupena Reserve, 31.07.2006, 1 ♂, at light, Y. Petrova leg. [BFUS]. **Danubian Plain:** Shumen Heights, 43°15'06.65"N, 26°55'12.97"E, 460 m a.s.l., 18.07.2011, 1 ♂, at light, O. Sivilov & B. Zlatkov leg. [BFUS]. **Black Sea Coast:** near the mouth of Kamchiya Riv., 42°59'31.32"N, 27°53'22.96"E, 1 m a.s.l., 25.07.2011, 1 ♂, at light, O. Sivilov & B. Zlatkov leg. [BFUS]. **Pirin Mt.:** along left-bank tributary of Burovitsa Riv., 1 km NE of Paril Vill., 41°26'37.8"N, 23°41'26.4"E, 805 m a.s.l., 02.08.2016, 1 ♀, at light, Y. Petrova & B. Zlatkov leg. [BFUS].

***Rhaesus serricollis* Motschulsky, 1838**

Black Sea coast: Ropotamo River, August 1985 [EM]. **Sandanski-Petrich Valley:** Rupite Vill., 19-25.06.1995, 2 ex. found under street lamps, V. Gashtarov leg. [VG]; Rupite place, 2.4 km SE of Ribnik Vill., right bank of Struma Riv., 41°28'4.02"N, 23°16'9.60"E, 90 m a.s.l., 11.08.2015, 1 ♀, at light, Y. Petrova & B. Zlatkov leg. [BFUS]. **Maleshvska Planina Mt.:** 1 km SE of Kamenitsa Vill., 41°38'32.88"N, 23°09'59.04"E, 239 m a.s.l., 30.07.2016, 1 ♂, at light, Y. Petrova & B. Zlatkov leg. [BFUS].

LEPTURINAE

***Alosterna tabacicolor tabacicolor* (DeGeer, 1775)**

Lyulin Mt.: Dupevitsa Peak, 25.05.2002, 3 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]. **Pirin Mt.:** Kalimantsi Vill., 280 m a.s.l., 21.05.-01.06.2002, 1 ex. found in Malaise trap, M. Langourov leg. [EM]. **Slavyanka Mt.:** SE of Petrovo Vill., near Izvora Chalet, 41°24'40.60"N, 23°33'34.95"E, 735 m a.s.l., 14.06.2014, 1 ♂, at light, O. Sivilov & B. Zlatkov leg. [BFUS]. **Lozenska Plnina Mt.:** 1 km SE of Lozen Vill., 42°35'21.90"N, 23°30'44.52"E, 880 m a.s.l., 12.06.2017, 4 ♂♂, 1 ♀, on flowers, D. Gradinarov leg. [BFUS]; 2 km SE of Lozen Vill., 42°35'20.82"N, 23°31'11.88"E, 978 m a.s.l., 12.06.2017, 4 ♂♂, on flowers of *Aegopodium podagraria* L., D. Gradinarov leg. [BFUS]; near Sveti Spas Monastery, 42°35'16.80"N, 23°31'17.34"E, 986 m a.s.l., 12.06.2017, 3 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀, on flowers, D. Gradinarov leg. [BFUS]; 1 km SE of Lozen Vill., 42°35'21.90"N, 23°30'44.52"E, 880 m a.s.l., 11.06.2018, 1 ♀, on flowers, D. Gradinarov leg. [BFUS]. **Danubian Plain:** Shumen Heights, near Shumen Fortress, 43°15'42.00"N, 26°53'27.52"E, 440 m a.s.l., 1.06.2019, 1 ♂, on flowers, O. Sivilov, B. Zlatkov & R. Beckchiev leg. [BFUS].

***Anastrangalia dubia dubia* (Scopoli, 1763)**

The Western Rhodopes: between Velingrad and Sarnitsa, 21.07.2001, 4 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]; S of Rakitovo Vill., Pashino Bardo place, 1500 m a.s.l.,

19.06.2007, 2 ♀♀, net sweeping, D. Gradinarov leg. [BFUS]. **Rila Mt.:** Borovets Resort, 1200 a.s.l., 26.07.2001, 1 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]; 1300 m a.s.l., 10.07.2002, 2 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]. **Black Sea coast:** Lozenets Vill., 24.06.2003, 1 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]. **Lozenska Planina Mt.:** 2 km SE of Lozen Vill., 42°35'20.82"N, 23°31'11.88"E, 978 m a.s.l., 12.06.2017, 1 ♂, on flowers of *Aegopodium podagraria* L., D. Gradinarov leg. [BFUS]; 1 km SE of Lozen Vill., 42°35'21.90"N, 23°30'44.52"E, 880 m a.s.l., 11.06.2018, 1 ♂, on flowers, D. Gradinarov leg. [BFUS].

***Anastrangalia sanguinolenta* (Linnaeus, 1760)**

The Western Rhodopes: between Yakoruda and Velingrad, 850 a.s.l., 20.07.2001, 2 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]; between Velingrad and Sarnitsa, 21.07.2001, 4 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]. **Rila Mt.:** Borovets Resort, 1200 a.s.l., 26.07.2001, 1 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]; Belmeken Peak, 2000 m a.s.l., 27.06.2002, 1 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]. **Pirin Mt.:** Bansko, 1500 m a.s.l., 21.06.2003, 1 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]. **Lozenska Planina Mt.:** 1 km SE of Lozen Vill., 42°35'21.90"N, 23°30'44.52"E, 880 m a.s.l., 11.06.2018, 1 ♂, 1 ♀, on flowers, D. Gradinarov leg. [BFUS].

***Anoplodera (Anoplodera) rufipes rufipes* (Schaller, 1783)**

Lyulin Mt.: Dupevitsa Peak, 25.05.2002, 1 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]. **Lozenska Planina Mt.:** Sinanitza Chalet, 06.06.2003, 1 ex., V. Gashtarov leg. [VG]; 1 km SE of Lozen Vill., 42°35'21.90"N, 23°30'44.52"E, 880 m a.s.l., 12.06.2017, 2 ♂♂, on flowers, D. Gradinarov leg. [BFUS]. **Sofia Region:** Iskar River Valley, from Pasarel Vill. to Dyavolskiya Most place, June 2018, 12 ex. on flowers of Umbrelliferae, V. Gashtarov leg. [VG].

***Etorofus (Etorofus) pubescens* (Fabricius, 1787)**

The Western Rhodopes: between Velingrad and Sarnitsa, 21.07.2001, 6 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM].

***Grammoptera (Grammoptera) abdominalis* (Stephens, 1831)**

Upper Thracian Plain: Sveti Ilia Hills, 3 km SW of Boyadzhik Vill., 42°22'44.4"N, 26°15'37.2"E, 240 m a.s.l., 17.04.2016, 4 ♂♂, at light, O. Sivilov & B. Zlatkov leg. [BFUS].

***Grammoptera (Grammoptera) ruficornis ruficornis* (Fabricius, 1781)**

Pirin Mt.: Sveti Ilia Hill near Kalimantsi Vill., 450-510 m a.s.l., 06.04.-10.05.2002, 1 ex. found in soil trap, M. Langourov leg. [EM]. **Lyulin Mt.:** Dupevitsa Peak, 25.05.2002, 3 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]. **Black Sea Coast:** NE of Kranevo, Baltata Reserve, 43°21'00.00"N, 28°04'20.00"E, 10 m a.s.l., 26.05.2012, 2 ♀♀, beating from trees, O. Sivilov & B. Zlatkov leg. [BFUS]. **Lozenska Planina Mt.:** 2 km SE of Lozen Vill., 42°35'20.82"N, 23°31'11.88"E, 978 m a.s.l., 12.06.2017, 1 ♀, on flowers of *Aegopodium podagraria* L., D. Gradinarov leg. [BFUS].

***Grammoptera (Grammoptera) ustulata ustulata* (Schaller, 1783)**

Upper Thracian Plain: Sveti Ilia Hills, 3 km SW of Boyadzhik Vill., 42°22'44.4"N, 26°15'37.2"E, 240 m a.s.l., 17.04.2016, 1 ♀, at light, O. Sivilov & B. Zlatkov leg. [BFUS].

***Pachytodes cerambyciformis* (Schrank, 1781)**

The Western Rhodopes: Grashevo Vill. near Velingrad, 21.07.2001, 4 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]. **Rila Mt.:** Rila Monastery, 1100 m a.s.l., 23.06.2002, 4 ex., E.

Migliaccio leg. [EM]. **The West Balkan Range:** Vrachanski Balkan, Sedemte prestola loc., 720 m a.s.l., 14.06.2003, 1 ex. found in yellow trap, E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]. **Strandzha Mt.:** Marina Reka Protected Area, 5 km north-east of Balgari Vill., 160 m a.s.l., 25-28.06.2003, 1 ex. [EM]. **Lozenska Plnina Mt.:** 1 km SE of Lozen Vill., 42°35'21.90"N, 23°30'44.52"E, 880 m a.s.l., 12.06.2017, 1 ♂, on flowers, D. Gradinarov leg. [BFUS]; the same locality, 11.06.2018, 1 ♂, on flowers, D. Gradinarov leg. [BFUS]; 2 km SE of Lozen Vill., 42°35'20.82"N, 23°31'11.88"E, 978 m a.s.l., 12.06.2017, 4 ♂♂, on flowers of *Aegopodium podagraria* L., D. Gradinarov leg. [BFUS].

***Pachytodes erraticus* (Dalman, 1817)**

Rila Mt.: Rila Monastery, 08.07.2001, 3 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]. **Pirin Mt.:** Bansko, between Bunderitsa Chalet and Vihren Peak, 1700 m a.s.l., 19.07.2001, 1 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]. **The Western Rhodopes:** Velingrad, 850 m a.s.l., 20.07.2001, 7 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]; Grashevo Vill. near Velingrad, 21.07.2001, 2 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]; Bachkovo Vill. near Asenovgrad, Bachkovo Monastery, 29.06.2002, 3 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]. **Black Sea coast:** Sozopol, Ropotamo Reserve, 26.06.2003, 1 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]. **Lozenska Plnina Mt.:** 1 km SE of Lozen Vill., 42°35'21.90"N, 23°30'44.52"E, 880 m a.s.l., 11.06.2018, 1 ♂, on flowers, D. Gradinarov leg. [BFUS].

***Pedostrangalia (Neosphenalia) verticalis* (Germar, 1822)**

Sandanski-Petrich Valley: 2 km south of Kamenitsa Vill. near Kresna, 170-240 m a.s.l., 09.05.2002, 2 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]. **Pirin Mt.:** 2 km W of Vlaha Vill., 41°44'20.64"N, 23°12'20.22"E, 465 m a.s.l., 28.05.2016, 1 ♀, on flowers, D. Gradinarov & Y. Petrova leg. [BFUS].

***Pedostrangalia (Pedostrangalia) revestita* (Linnaeus, 1767)**

Sandanski-Petrich Valley: near Novo Hodzhovo Vill., 41°24'26.00"N, 23°24'27.00"E, 115 m a.s.l., 05.05.2013, 1 ♀, at light, O. Sivilov & B. Zlatkov leg. [BFUS]. **Remark:** Rare species in Bulgaria (Migliaccio et al., 2007).

***Rutpela maculata maculata* (Poda von Neuhaus, 1761)**

Rila Mt.: Rila Monastery, 08.07.2001, 1 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]. **The Western Rhodopes:** between Velingrad and Sarnitsa, fork to Grashevo Vill., 21.07.2001, 1 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]. **Lozenska Planina Mt.:** 2 km SE of Lozen Vill., 42°35'20.82"N, 23°31'11.88"E, 978 m a.s.l., 12.06.2017, 1 ♂, on flowers of *Aegopodium podagraria* L., D. Gradinarov leg. [BFUS].

***Stenurella (Nigrostenurella) nigra nigra* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Pirin Mt.: Kalimanska River, Kalimantsi Vill., 12.05.2002, 1 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]; Kalimantsi Vill., 280 m a.s.l., 12-21.05.2002, 1 ex. found in Malaise trap, I. Samardzhiev leg. [EM]; Sveti Ilia Hill near Kalimantsi Vill., 450-510 m a.s.l., 01-22.06.2002, 1 ex. found in tree trap, M. Langourov leg. [EM]. **Lozenska Plnina Mt.:** 1 km SE of Lozen Vill., 42°35'21.90"N, 23°30'44.52"E, 880 m a.s.l., 12.06.2017, 1 ♂, on flowers, D. Gradinarov leg. [BFUS].

***Stenurella (Priscostenurella) bifasciata bifasciata* (O. F. Müller, 1776)**

The Western Rhodopes: between Yakoruda and Velingrad, 850 m a.s.l., 20.07.2001, 1 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]; Batak, Batak Lake, 1140 m a.s.l.,

28.06.2002, 2 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]. **Rila Mt.:** Borovets Resort, 1200 m a.s.l., 26.07.2001, 1 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]. **Pirin Mt.:** Sveti Ilia Hill near Kalimantsi Vill., 450-510 m a.s.l., 01-22.06.2002, 2 ex. found in tree traps, M. Langourov leg. [EM]. **West Balkan Range:** Svoge, 600 m a.s.l., 16.06.2002, 1 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]. **Sandanski-Petrich Valley:** 2 km south of Kamenitsa Vill. near Kresna, 170-240 m a.s.l., 31.05.-08.08.2002, 9 ex. found in tree traps, D. Chobanov leg. [EM].

Stenurella (Priscostenurella) septempunctata septempunctata (Fabricius, 1793)

Pirin Mt.: Bansko, between Bunderitsa Chalet and Vihren Peak, 1700-1750 m a.s.l., 18-19.07.2001, 2 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]; Sveti Ilia Hill near Kalimantsi Vill., 450-510 m a.s.l., 01-22.06.2002, 2 ex. found in tree traps, M. Langourov leg. [EM]. **The Western Rhodopes:** between Yakoruda and Velingrad, 850 m a.s.l., 20.07.2001, 4 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]; between Dospat and Smolyan, 22.07.2001, 1 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]. **Sandanski-Petrich Valley:** 2 km south of Kamenitsa Vill. near Kresna, 170-240 m a.s.l., 09.05.-23.06.2002, 3 ex. found in tree traps, M. Langourov and D. Chobanov leg. [EM]. **West Balkan Range:** Svoge, 600 m a.s.l., 16.06.2002, 2 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]. **Rila Mt.:** Rila Monastery, 1100 m a.s.l., 23.06.2002, 2 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]. **Maleshevska Planina Mt.:** Gorna Breznitsa Vill., 800-900 m a.s.l., 31.07.2002, 1 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM].

Stenurella (Stenurella) melanura melanura (Linnaeus, 1758)

The Western Rhodopes: between Yakoruda and Velingrad, 850 m a.s.l., 20.07.2001, 1 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]; Yugovo Vill. near Laki, 650 m a.s.l., 30.06.-26.07.2003, 1 ex. found in tree trap, M. Langourov leg. [EM]. **Sandanski-Petrich Valley:** 2 km south of Kamenitsa Vill. near Kresna, 170-240 m a.s.l., 31.05.-23.06.2002, 3 ex. found in tree traps, M. Langourov leg. [EM]. **Pirin Mt.:** Sveti Ilia Hill near Kalimantsi Vill., 450-510 m a.s.l., 01-22.06.2002, 1 ex. found in tree trap, M. Langourov leg. [EM]. **Maleshevska Planina Mt.:** Dolni Laki Vill., 650 m a.s.l., 02-07.07.2002, 1 ex. found in soil traps, S. Lazarov and T. Ljubomirov leg. [EM].

Stictoleptura (Aredolpona) rubra rubra (Linnaeus, 1758)

The Western Rhodopes: between Velingrad and Sarnitsa, 21.07.2001, 2 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]. **Rila Mt.:** Borovets Resort, 1200 m a.s.l., 26.07.2001, 1 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]. **Maleshevska Planina Mt.:** Dolni Laki Vill., 650 m a.s.l., 02-30.07.2002, 1 ex. found in soil trap, S. Lazarov and T. Ljubomirov leg. [EM].

Stictoleptura (Maculileptura) maculicornis (DeGeer, 1775)

Rila Mt.: Borovets Resort, 1200 m a.s.l., 26.07.2001, 1 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM].

Stictoleptura (Maculileptura) pallens (Brullé, 1832)

Pirin Mt.: 2 km W of Vlaha Vill., 41°44'20.64"N, 23°12'20.22"E, 465 m a.s.l., 28.05.2016, 1 ♀, on flowers, D. Gradinarov & Y. Petrova leg. [BFUS].

Stictoleptura (Melanoleptura) scutellata scutellata (Fabricius, 1781)

Strandzha Mt.: Marina Reka Protected Area, 5 km north-east of Balgari Vill., 160 m a.s.l., 25-28.06.2003, 1 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]. **Pirin Mt.:** SE of Pirin Vill., 41°31'18.90"N, 23°34'42.22"E, 885 m a.s.l., 22.07.2010, 1 ♂, net sweeping, O. Sivilov, B. Zlatkov & R. Beckchiev leg. [BFUS]. **Lozenska Planina Mt.:** 2 km SE of

Lozen Vill., 42°35'20.82"N, 23°31'11.88"E, 978 m a.s.l., 12.06.2017, 3 ♂♂, on flowers of *Aegopodium podagraria* L., D. Gradinarov leg. [BFUS]; 1 km SE of Lozen Vill., 42°35'21.90"N, 23°30'44.52"E, 880 m a.s.l., 11.06.2018, 1 ♂, on flowers, D. Gradinarov leg. [BFUS].

***Stictoleptura (Paracorymbia) fulva* (DeGeer, 1775)**

The Western Rhodopes: Bachkovo Vill. near Asenovgrad, Bachkovo Monastery, 29.06.2002, 1 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]. **Pirin Mt.:** Bansko, Bunderitsa meadow loc., 18.07.2001, E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]; 3 km SW of Stara Kresna Vill., 41°45'48.48"N, 23°10'11.40"E, 455 m a.s.l., 02.07.2016, 1 ♀, on flowers, D. Gradinarov & Y. Petrova leg. [BFUS].

***Stictoleptura (Stictoleptura) cordigera cordigera* (Füsslins, 1775)**

Black Sea coast: Lozenets Vill., 24.06.2003, 1 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM].

***Strangalia attenuata* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

The Western Rhodopes: Velingrad, 850 m a.s.l., 20.07.2001, 1 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]; between Dospat and Smolyan, 22.07.2001, 1 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM].

***Cortodera femorata* (Fabricius, 1787)**

The Eastern Rhodopes: Madzharovo, 01-03.05.2003, abundant (more than 200 ex.) collected on white and UW light, V. Gashtarov leg. [VG]; Ivaylovgrad, 04.05.2003, abundant (more than 100 ex.) collected on white and UW light, V. Gashtarov leg. [VG]. **Ograzhden Mt.:** Churicheni Vill. near Petrich, 900 m a.s.l., 15-30.06.2003, 1 ex. found in Malaise trap, O. Todorov leg. [EM].

***Cortodera flavimana flavimana* (Waltl, 1838)**

Lyulin Mt.: Dupevitsa Peak, 25.05.2002, 2 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]. **Sandanski-Petrich Valley:** 2 km south of Kamenitsa Vill. near Kresna, 170-240 m a.s.l., 09-31.05.2002, 1 ex., M. Langourov leg. [EM].

***Cortodera humeralis humeralis* (Schaller, 1783)**

Lyulin Mt.: Dupevitsa Peak, 25.05.2002, 2 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]. **Maleshvska Planina Mt.:** Mikrevo Vill., 310 m a.s.l., 05.07.2002, 1 ex., S. Lazarov leg. [EM]. **Pirin Mt.:** Sveti Ilia Hill near Kalimantsi Vill., 450-510 m a.s.l., 06.04.-01.06.2002, 9 ex. found in soil traps, M. Langourov leg. [EM]. **Dobrudzha:** SE of Bulgarka Vill., 44°00'25.46"N, 27°20'57.69"E, 70 m a.s.l., 29.04.2012, 1 ex., at light, O. Sivilov & B. Zlatkov leg. [BFUS]. **Upper Thracian Plain:** Sveti Ilia Hills, 3 km SW of Boyadzhik Vill., 42°22'44.4"N, 26°15'37.2"E, 240 m a.s.l., 17.04.2016, 22 ex., at light, O. Sivilov & B. Zlatkov leg. [BFUS].

***Dinoptera collaris* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Pirin Mt.: Sveti Ilia Hill near Kalimantsi Vill., 450-510 m a.s.l., 10-11.05.2002, 1 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]; Kalimantsi Vill., 500 m a.s.l., 06.05.2003, 1 ex., S. Lazarov leg. [EM]. **Lyulin Mt.:** Dupevitsa Peak, 25.05.2002, 3 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]. **Struma-Petrich Valley:** 2 km south of Kamenitsa Vill. near Kresna, 170-240 m a.s.l., 09.05.2002, 1 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]. **Rila Mt.:** Rila Monastery, 1100 m a.s.l., 23.06.2002, 2 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]. **Lozenska Plnina Mt.:** 1 km SE of Lozen Vill., 42°35'21.90"N, 23°30'44.52"E, 880 m a.s.l., 12.06.2017, 4 ♂♂, 3 ♀♀, on flowers, D. Gradinarov leg. [BFUS].

***Carilia virginea virginea* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

The Western Rhodopes: S of Rakitovo Vill., Pashino Bardo place, 1500 m a.s.l., 19.06.2007, 2 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀, net sweeping, D. Gradinarov leg. [BFUS].

***Gnathacmaeops pratensis* (Laicharting, 1784)**

Osogovska Planina Mt.: Trite Buki place, 42°10'28.5"N, 22°37'29.5"E, 1560 m a.s.l., 25.06.2017, 7 ♂♂, on flowers, D. Gradinarov leg. [BFUS].

***Pachyta quadrimaculata* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

The Western Rhodopes: Karatepe place near Velingrad, 1500 m a.s.l., 21.07.2001, 2 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]; Yundola Vill., 28.06.2002, 2 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]; Mantaritsa Reserve, Skelite place, 18.07.2007, 1 ♂, D. Gradinarov leg. [BFUS]; Chudnite Mostove place, 1450 m a.s.l., 29.07.2017, 3 ex. on flowers of *Sambucus ebulus* L., V. Gashtarov leg. [VG]. **Rila Mt.:** Borovets Resort, 1300 m a.s.l., 10.07.2002, 1 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM].

***Rhagium (Rhagium) bifasciatum* Fabricius, 1775**

The Western Rhodopes: Mantaritsa Reserve, Skelite place, 18.6.2007, 1 ♂, 1 ♀, D. Gradinarov leg. [BFUS]. **Pirin Mt.:** E of Pirin Vill., 41°32'41.00"N, 23°36'14.00"E, 1580 m a.s.l., 14.06.2010, 1 ♀, hand collection, O. Sivilov & B. Zlatkov leg. [BFUS].

***Rhagium (Megarhagium) mordax* (De Geer, 1775)**

Osogovska Planina Mt.: near Trite Buki Chalet, 18.11.2001, 2 ♀, under bark, D. Gradinarov & Y. Petrova leg. [BFUS].

***Rhagium (Rhagium) inquisitor inquisitor* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Pirin Mt.: Bansko, Vihren Peak, 2350 m a.s.l., 23–24.06.2002, 1 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]; NE of Ilindentsi Vill., 41°42'28.81"N, 23°18'32.14"E, 1605 m a.s.l., 09.09.2011, 1 ♂, in decaying logs, O. Sivilov & B. Zlatkov leg. [BFUS]. **Rila Mt.:** near Bodrost Chalet, 42°02'33.33"N, 23°20'46.13"E, 1360 m a.s.l., 21.08.2011, 1 ♀, O. Sivilov & B. Zlatkov leg. [BFUS].

***Stenocorus (Stenocorus) meridianus* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Lozenska Planina Mt.: Sinanitza Chalet, 06.06.2003, 1 ex., V. Gashtarov leg. [VG]. **Danubian Plain:** Shumen Heights, near Shumen Fortress, 43°15'42.00"N, 26°53'27.52"E, 440 m a.s.l., 1.06.2019, 1 ♀, on flowers, O. Sivilov, B. Zlatkov & R. Beckchiev leg. [BFUS].

***Rhamnusium bicolor bicolor* (Schrank, 1781)**

Sandanski-Petrich Valley: Melnishka Reka River, Novo Konomladi Vill., 24.05.1996, 7 ex. collected in a hollow of a tree of *Populus* sp., V. Gashtarov leg. [VG]; the same locality and tree, 19.05.2005, 2 ex., V. Gashtarov leg. [VG]; Rupite Vill., 03.05.2002, 1 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]; Topolnitsa Vill., 05.06.2018, 1 ex. in a hollow of a tree of *Populus* sp., V. Gashtarov leg. [VG]. **The Western Rhodopes:** Asenovgrad, Railway station, 210 m a.s.l., 1 ex. on *Aesculus hippocastanum* L., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM].

***Xylosteus bartoni* Obenberger et Maran, 1933**

Pirin Mt.: Bansko, Vihren Peak, 2350 m a.s.l., 23–24.06.2002, 1 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]; 9 km SW of Razlog Town, "Bayuvi Dupki – Dzhindzhiritsa" Reserve, 41°49'24.67"N, 23°23'07.31"E, 1770 m a.s.l., 09.7.2012, 1 ♀, O. Sivilov & B. Zlatkov

leg. [BFUS]. **The Western Rhodopes:** above Trigrad Vill., 07.06.2009, 1 ex. under a fallen tree of *Picea abies* H.Karst., V. Gashtarov leg. [VG].

NECYDALINAE

Necydalis (Necydalis) major Linnaeus, 1758

Sofia Region: Sofia City, 15-20.06.2002, 2 ex. collected flying around cherry (*Prunus cerasus* L.), V. Gashtarov leg. [VG].

SPONDYLIDINAE

Alocerus moesiacus (Frivaldszky von Frivald, 1837)

Pirin Mt.: 3 km NE of Kalimantsi Vill., road to the Belyovo Vill., Sveti Ilia Hill, 41°28'00.24"N, 23°31'00.78"E, 400 m a.s.l., 01.08.2016, 3 ♂♂, 1 ♀, at light, Y. Petrova & B. Zlatkov leg. [BFUS]. **Remark:** Rare species in Bulgaria (Migliaccio et al., 2007).

Anisarhron barbipes (Schrank, 1781)

Sofia Region: Sofia, Lozenets District, 42°40'43"N, 23°19'20"E, 565 m a.s.l., 18.6.2009, 1 ♀, O. Sivilov leg. [BFUS]. **Remark:** Rare species in Bulgaria (Migliaccio et al., 2007).

Arhopalus ferus (Mulsant, 1839)

West Balkan Range: Svoge, 600 m a.s.l., 31.08.2002, 1 ex., G. Hristova leg. [EM].

Arhopalus rusticus rusticus (Linnaeus, 1758)

The Western Rhodopes: Yundola Vill., 1460 m a.s.l., 22.06.2003, 1 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]. **Black Sea coast:** Ropotamo Reserve near Sozopol, 26.06.2003, 1 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]; S of Kranevo Vill., Zlatni Pyasatsi Nature Park, 43°20'02.97"N, 28°03'37.19"E, 160 m a.s.l., 24.07.2011, 2 ♂♂, 1 ♀, at light, O. Sivilov & B. Zlatkov leg. [BFUS]. **Strandzha Mt.:** Marina Reka Protected Area, 5 km north-east of Balgari Vill., 160 m a.s.l., 25-28.06.2003, 1 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]. **Central Balkan Range:** N of Kalofer, Central Balkan National Park, 42°40'46.84"N, 24°58'53.65"E, 1220 m a.s.l., 28.07.2011, 1 ♀, at light, O. Sivilov & B. Zlatkov leg. [BFUS]; Mikre heights, SW of Mikre Vill., 43°01'15.65"N, 24°30'11.54"E, 605 m a.s.l., 06.08.2011, 1 ♀, at light, O. Sivilov & B. Zlatkov leg. [BFUS]. **Sofia Region:** Beledie han Vill., 01.07.2019, 2 ex. attracted by light, V. Gashtarov leg. [VG].

Asemum striatum (Linnaeus, 1758)

Zemen gorge: Zemen, near the railway station, 42°28'48.78"N, 22°44'49.92"E, 600 m a.s.l., 03.06.2012, 11 ex., on trunks of *Thuja* sp., D. Gradinarov & G. Hristov leg. [BFUS].

Saphanus piceus ganglbaueri Brancsik, 1886

The Western Rhodopes: SW of Yugovo Vill., 800 m a.s.l., 20.06.-28.07.2004, 1 ex. found in soil trap, E. Migliaccio leg. [EM].

Saphanus piceus piceus Laicharting, 1784

Sofia Region: Pasarel Vill., 710 m a.s.l., 16.07.-01.09.2004, 1 ex. found in soil trap, E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]. **Lozenska Planina Mt.:** S of Lozen Vill., 42°34'48.77"N, 23°29'17.85"E, 1050 m a.s.l., 10.06.2012, 1 ♂, at night with a headlamp, O. Sivilov & B. Zlatkov leg. [BFUS].

***Spondylis buprestoides* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

The Western Rhodopes: Dospat Lake near Sarnitsa, 1200 m a.s.l., 26.05.2002, 1 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM].

***Tetropium castaneum* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Rila Mt.: N of Deno Peak, 42°12'10.80"N, 23°36'17.40"E, 2630 m a.s.l., 23.6.2013, 1 ♀, on snow patches, O. Sivilov & B. Zlatkov leg. [BFUS].

CERAMBYCINAE

***Icosium tomentosum atticum* Ganglbauer, 1882**

Maleshevska Planina Mt.: 1 km SE of Kamenitsa Vill., 41°38'33.12"N, 23°10'02.70"E, 220 m a.s.l., 30.07.2016, 1 ♂, at light, Y. Petrova & B. Zlatkov leg. [BFUS]. **Pirin Mt.:** 1 km NE of Kalimantsi Vill., 41°27'54.13"N, 23°29'19.48"E, 315 m a.s.l., 28.06.2019, 1 ♂, at light, O. Sivilov & B. Zlatkov leg. [BFUS]. **Remark:** Rare species in Bulgaria (Migliaccio et al., 2007).

***Anaglyptus (Anaglyptus) mysticus* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Lyulin Mt.: Dupevitsa Peak, 25.05.2002, 1 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]. **Rila Mt.:** Rila Monastery, 1100 m a.s.l., 23.06.2002, 1 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]. **Western Balkan Range:** S of Belogradchik, 43°37'02.36"N, 22°41'19.92"E, 450 m a.s.l., 08.05.2008, 1 ♀, net sweeping, O. Sivilov leg. [BFUS]. **Lozenska Planina Mt.:** 2 km SE of Lozen Vill., near Sveti Spas Monastery, 42°35'16.80"N, 23°31'17.34"E, 986 m a.s.l., 12.06.2017, 1 ♀, on flowers, D. Gradinarov leg. [BFUS].

***Paraclytus sexguttatus* (Adams, 1817)**

Strandzha Mt.: on the road between Balgari Vill. and Izgrev Vill., 42°07'03.76"N, 27°45'56.89"E, 250 m a.s.l., 08.05.2009, 1 ♀, on flowers of *Crataegus* sp., O. Sivilov, R. Beckchiev & R. Kostova leg. [BFUS]. **Remark:** Rare species in Bulgaria (Migliaccio et al., 2007). It was previously reported from the same locality, Izgrev Vill. (Georgiev et al., 2015).

***Callidium violaceum* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

West Balkan Range: Vrachanski Balkan, Milanovo Vill., 850 m a.s.l., 13.05.2004, 1 ex., S. Beshkov leg. [EM]; Gorni Lom Vill., 500 m a.s.l., 11.05.2019, 1 ex., G. Georgiev leg. [GG]. **Remark:** The species is new for the West Balkan Range.

***Lioderina linearis* (Hampe, 1871)**

Black Sea coast: Varna, 03.06.1963, 2 ex., J. Sekera leg. [EM]. **Remark:** The species was considered rare in Bulgaria (Migliaccio et al., 2007). However, it was subsequently found in a number of places, including twice at the same locality in Varna (Sabol, 2000; Gradinarov, Sivilov, 2017).

***Phymatodes (Phymatodes) testaceus* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Pirin Mt.: Kalimantsi Vill., 12.05.2002, 2 ex., D. Chobanov leg. [EM]; Kalimantsi Vill., 280 m a.s.l., 12.05.-01.06.2002, 3 ex. found in Malaise trap, M. Langourov and I. Samardzhiev leg. [EM]. **West Balkan Range:** Vrachanski Balkan, Milanovo Vill., 850 m a.s.l., 14.06.2003, 1 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]. **Strandzha Mt.:** Marina Reka Protected Area, 5 km north-east of Balgari Vill., 160 m a.s.l., 25-28.06.2003, 3 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM].

***Phymatodes (Phymatodellus) rufipes rufipes* (Fabricius, 1777)**

Lyulin Mt.: Dupevitsa Peak, 25.05.2002, 1 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]. **Golo Bardo Mt.:** Pernik Region, 13.05.2004, 7 ex. collected on branches of *Crataegus* sp., V. Gashtarov leg. [VG]. **Lozenska Planina Mt.:** Darvodeleca place, 09.05.2017, 3 ex. collected on flowers of *Crataegus monogina* Jacq., V. Gashtarov leg. [VG].

***Pyrrhodium sanguineum* Linnaeus, 1758**

Sofia Region: Dragoman, Dragomansko Blato Lake, 24.04.2004, 1 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]. **The Western Rhodopes:** Byaga Vill., 27.03.2017, 1 ♀, D. Kaynarov leg. [BFUS].

***Ropalopus (Ropalopus) clavipes* (Fabricius, 1775)**

West Balkan Range: Vrachanski Balkan, Milanovo Vill., 850 m a.s.l., 24.07.-05.08.2004, 4 ex., E. Migliaccio and S. Beshkov leg. [EM].

***Cerambyx (Cerambyx) cerdo cerdo* Linnaeus, 1758**

Strandzha Mt.: Marina Reka Protected Area, 5 km north-east of Balgari Vill., 160 m a.s.l., 25-28.06.2003, 3 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM].

***Cerambyx (Cerambyx) miles* Bonelli, 1823**

Sandanski-Petrich Valley: Novo Konomladi Vill., 29.06.1996, 1 ex.; 05-10.07.2005, 1 ex., V. Gashtarov leg. [VG]. **Pirin Mt.:** Sveti Ilia Hill near Kalimantsi Vill., 22.06.-06.08.2002, 1 ex., D. Chobanov leg. [EM]; 08.07.-12.08.2003, 1 ex., M. Langourov leg. [VG].

***Cerambyx (Microcerambyx) scopolii scopolii* Fuessly, 1775**

Strandzha Mt.: Marina Reka Protected Area, 5 km north-east of Balgari Vill., 160 m a.s.l., 25-28.06.2003, 2 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM].

***Chlorophorus (Crassofasciatus) aegyptiacus* (Fabricius, 1775)**

Sandanski-Petrich Valley: Kresna Gorge, 17.07.2001, 2 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]; Sheitan Dere River, 5 km north of Kresna, 250 m a.s.l., 01.08.2002, 10 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]; Sheitan Dere River, 41°45'36.02"N, 23°09'29.91"E, 290 m a.s.l., 20.07.2010, 1 ♂, net sweeping, O. Sivilov, B. Zlatkov & R. Beckchiev leg. [BFUS]; Rupite place, 41°26'46.80"N, 23°16'21.60"E, 90 m a.s.l., 25.7.2010, 1 ♂, O. Sivilov, B. Zlatkov & R. Beckchiev leg. [BFUS]. **Maleshevska Planina Mt.:** Mikrevo Vill., 260 m a.s.l., 02-30.07.2002, 2 ex., S. Lazarov and T. Ljubomirov leg. [EM]; Tsaparevo Vill., 480 m a.s.l., 30.07.2002, 1 ex., S. Lazarov and T. Ljubomirov leg. [EM]; Novo Konomladi Vill., 23.07.2017, 8 ex. on flowers of *Eryngium campestre* L., V. Gashtarov leg. [VG].

***Chlorophorus (Crassofasciatus) hungaricus* Seidlitz, 1891**

Sandanski-Petrich Valley: Novo Konomladi Vill., 31.05.2000, many specimens on flowers of *Lotus herbaceus* (Vill.) Jauzein, V. Gashtarov leg. [VG].

***Chlorophorus (Crassofasciatus) trifasciatus* (Fabricius, 1781)**

Sandanski-Petrich Valley: near Novo Hodzhovo Vill., 41°24'21.45"N, 23°24'52.51"E, 175 m a.s.l., 15.06.2010, 1 ♀, net sweeping, O. Sivilov & B. Zlatkov leg. [BFUS].

***Chlorophorus (Humeromaculatus) figuratus* (Scopoli, 1763)**

Pirin Mt.: Kalimantsi Vill., 280 m a.s.l., 12-21.05.2002, 1 ex., I. Samardzhiev leg. [EM]. **West Balkan Range:** Vrachanski Balkan, Gorna Bela Rechka Vill., 420 m a.s.l., 25.05.2003, 1 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM].

***Chlorophorus (Immaculatus) herbstii* (Brahm, 1790)**

The Western Rhodopes: Chepelare Region, Orehovo Vill., 25-26.07.2005, 2 ex. collected on flowers of Umbrelliferae, V. Gashtarov and G. Murzov leg. [VG].

***Chlorophorus (Immaculatus) varius varius* (O. F. Müller, 1766)**

Struma-Petrich Valley: 2 km south of Kamenitsa Vill. near Kresna, 170-240 m a.s.l., 23.06.-08.08.2002, 1 ex. found in tree trap, D. Chobanov leg. [EM]; Kresna Gorge, Peyo Yavorov Railway Station, 19.07.2002, 1 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]; Sheitan Dere River, 5 km north of Kresna, 250 m a.s.l., 01.08.2002, 2 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]. **Maleshevska Planina Mt.:** Gorna Breznitsa Vill., 550-900 m a.s.l., 31.07.-01.08.2002, 4 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM].

***Chlorophorus (Perderomaculatus) sartor* (Müller, 1766)**

Pirin Mt.: Bansko, Bunderitsa loc., 1750 m a.s.l., 18.07.2001, 1 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]; Sheitan Dere River, 41°45'36.02"N, 23°09'29.91"E, 290 m a.s.l., 20.07.2010, 2 ♀♀, net sweeping, O. Sivilov, B. Zlatkov & R. Beckchiev leg. [BFUS]; 3 km SW of Stara Kresna Vill., 41°45'48.48"N, 23°10'11.40"E, 455 m a.s.l., 02.07.2016, 1 ♀, on flowers, D. Gradinarov & Y. Petrova leg. [BFUS]. **Strandzha Mt.:** Marina Reka Protected Area, 5 km north-east of Balgari Vill., 160 m a.s.l., 25-28.06.2003, 1 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM].

***Clytus (Clytus) arietis arietis* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Lyulin Mt.: Dupevitsa Peak, 25.05.2002, 1 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM].

***Clytus (Clytus) rhamni rhamni* Germar, 1817**

Struma-Petrich Valley: 2 km south of Kamenitsa Vill. near Kresna, 170-240 m a.s.l., 09.05.2002, 3 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]. **Maleshevska Planina Mt.:** Gorna Breznitsa Vill., 30-31.07.2002, 1 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]. **The Western Rhodopes:** Bachkovo Vill. near Asenovgrad, Bachkovo Monastery, 29.06.2002, 1 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]. **Black Sea coast:** Lozenets Vill., 24.06.2003, 3 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM].

***Echinocerus floralis* (Pallas, 1773)**

Sandanski-Petrich Valley: S of Katuntsi Vill., 41°26'08.20"N, 23°25'42.23"E, 150 m a.s.l., 14.06.2010, 1 ♀, net sweeping, O. Sivilov & B. Zlatkov leg. [BFUS]; near Novo Hodzhovo Vill., 41°24'21.45"N, 23°24'52.51"E, 175 m a.s.l., 15.06.2010, 1 ♀, net sweeping, O. Sivilov & B. Zlatkov leg. [BFUS].

***Isotomus speciosus speciosus* (D. H. Schneider, 1787)**

West Balkan Range: Vrachanski Balkan, Milanovo Vill., 950 m a.s.l., 04-05.08.2004, 1 ex., S. Beshkov leg. [EM]. **Struma-Petrich Valley:** Goleshovo Vill., 18.07.2016, 990 m a.s.l., 1 ex. in cut wood of *Quercus* sp., V. Gashtarov leg. [VG].

***Plagionotus arcuatus arcuatus* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Strandzha Mt.: Marina Reka Protected Area, 5 km north-east of Balgari Vill., 160 m a.s.l., 25-28.06.2003, 7 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]. **The Western Rhodopes:** Byaga Vill., 26.04.2008, 1 ♂, D. Kaynarov leg. [BFUS].

***Plagionotus detritus detritus* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Strandzha Mt.: Marina reka protected area, 5 km north-east of Balgari Vill., 160 m a.s.l., 25-28.06.2003, 26 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM].

***Xylotrechus (Xylotrechus) antilope antilope* (Schoenherr, 1817)**

Strandzha Mt.: Marina Reka Protected Area, 5 km NE of Balgari Vill., 160 m a.s.l., 25-28.06.2003, 22 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]; Ropotamo Reserve near Sozopol, 26.06.2003, 1 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM].

***Xylotrechus (Xylotrechus) arvicola arvicola* (Olivier, 1795)**

Black Sea coast: Ahtopol, 27.07.2003, 1 ex., Z. Hubenov leg. [EM].

***Rosalia alpina* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Maleshevska Planina Mt.: Gorna Breznitsa Vill., 800-900 m a.s.l., 30.07.2002, 1 ex., T. Ljubomirov leg. [EM].

***Deilus fugax* (Olivier, 1790)**

Sandanski-Petrich Valley: Marikostenska Tumba place (between Novo Konomladi and Marikostinovo Vill.), April 2005, 1 ex. found death on flowers of *Crataegus* sp., V. Gashtyarov leg. [VG].

***Axinopalpis gracilis gracilis* (Krynicky, 1832)**

Ograzhden Mt.: Krushitsa Vill., July 2007, 1 ex., V. Gashtyarov leg. [VG]. **Pirin Mt.:** near Kalimantsi Vill., 14.07.2013, 1 ex. on light, V. Gashtyarov leg. [VG]. **Sandanski-Petrich Valley:** near Novo Hodjovo Vill., 41°24'26.58"N 23°24'25.14"E, 115 m a.s.l., 14.06.2010, 1 ♂, at light, O. Sivilov & B. Zlatkov leg. [BFUS]. **Central Balkan Range:** N of Kalofer, Central Balkan National Park, 42°40'46.84"N, 24°58'53.65"E, 1220 m a.s.l., 28.07.2011, 1 ♂, at light, O. Sivilov & B. Zlatkov leg. [BFUS]. **Vlahina Mt.:** Oranovski Prolom Gorge, NW of Zheleznitsa Vill., 41°55'45.18"N, 23°05'21.83"E, 510 m a.s.l., 11.06.2012, 1 ♂, at light, O. Sivilov & B. Zlatkov leg. [BFUS]. **Pirin Mt.:** E of Ilindentsi Vill., 41°39'10.44"N, 23°14'44.28"E, 540 m a.s.l., 13.06.2012, 1 ♂, at light, O. Sivilov & B. Zlatkov leg. [BFUS]; above Sandanski, SW of Lilyanovo Vill., 41°36'44.85"N, 23°18'42.90"E, 470 m a.s.l., 27.06.2019, 1 ♂, 2 ♀♀, at light, O. Sivilov & B. Zlatkov leg. [BFUS]; 1 km NE of Kalimantsi Vill., 41°27'54.13"N, 23°29'19.48"E, 315 m a.s.l., 28.06.2019, 1 ♂, at light, O. Sivilov & B. Zlatkov leg. [BFUS]. **Upper Thracian Plain:** Sveti Ilia Hills, 3 km SW of Boyadzhik Vill., 42°22'44.83"N, 26°15'36.69"E, 240 m a.s.l., 29.06.2012, 1 ♂, at light, O. Sivilov & B. Zlatkov leg. [BFUS].

***Penichroa fasciata* (Stephens, 1831)**

Sandanski-Petrich Valley: Novo Konomladi Vill., July 2014, 1 dead ex. in dead wood of *Prunus*, V. Gashtyarov leg. [VG].

***Stromatium auratum* (Böber, 1793)**

Sandanski-Petrich Valley: Novo Konomladi Vill., 02.07.1992, 2 ex. collected on street lamp, V. Gashtarov leg. [VG]; Novo Konomladi Vill., 11 ex. reared from stem of common fig (*Ficus carica* L.), sample collection – 13-15.03.2003, adult emergence – July 2003, V. Gashtarov leg. [VG].

***Trichoferus griseus* (Fabricius, 1793)**

Sandanski-Petrich Valley: Novo Konomladi Vill., 14 ex. reared from stem of *Ficus carica* L., sample collection – 13-15.03.2003, adult emergence – July 2003, V. Gashtarov leg. [VG].

***Trichoferus pallidus* (Olivier, 1790)**

Black Sea coast: 2 km NW of Emona Vill., 42°43'57.3"N, 27°52'35.02"E, 190 m a.s.l., 18-19.8.2011, 1 ♀, at light, O. Sivilov & B. Zlatkov leg. [BFUS].

***Molorchus minor minor* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Pirin Mt.: Bansko, Vihren Peak, 2350 m a.s.l., 23-24.06.2002, 1 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]. **The Western Rhodopes:** S of Rakitovo Vill., Pashino Bardo place, 1500 m a.s.l., 19.06.2007, 2 ♂♂, 6 ♀♀, net sweeping, D. Gradinarov leg. [BFUS].

***Molorchus (Molorchus) umbellatarum umbellatarum* (Schreber, 1759)**

East Balkan Range: E of Yunets Vill., near Fandakliyska River, 42°55'51.00"N, 27°47'26.00"E, 60 m a.s.l., 24.05.2009, 1 ♀, net sweeping, O. Sivilov leg. [BFUS].

Black Sea coast: NE of Tuzlata place, 43°24'32.39"N, 28°13'54.80"E, 120 m a.s.l., 23.05.2012, 1 ♀, beating from trees, at night, O. Sivilov & B. Zlatkov leg. [BFUS]; N of Albena Resort, 43°22'57.07"N, 28°04'21.74"E, 225 m a.s.l., 26.05.2012, 1 ♂, beating from *Quercus* sp. and from *Carpinus* sp., O. Sivilov & B. Zlatkov leg. [BFUS].

Lozenska Planina Mt.: 2 km SE of Lozen Vill., 42°35'20.82"N, 23°31'11.88"E, 978 m a.s.l., 12.06.2017, 1 ♂, on flowers of *Aegopodium podagraria* L., D. Gradinarov leg. [BFUS].

***Obrium brunneum* (Fabricius, 1793)**

Vitosha Mt.: Bay Krastio loc., 07.06.2003, 1 ex., V. Gashtarov leg. [VG]. **Pirin Mt.:** near Banderitsa Chalet, 41°45'57.00"N, 23°25'26.00"E, 1820 m a.s.l., 19.07.2010, 1 ex., net sweeping, O. Sivilov, B. Zlatkov & R. Beckchiev leg. [BFUS].

***Obrium cantharinum cantharinum* (Linnaeus, 1767)**

The Western Rhodopes: Kupena Reserve, 31.07.2006, 1 ♂, at light, Y. Petrova leg. [BFUS]. **Sandanski-Petrich Valley:** near Novo Hodzhovo Vill., 41°24'26.58"N, 23°24'25.14"E, 115 m a.s.l., 14.06.2010, 1 ♂, at light, O. Sivilov & B. Zlatkov leg. [BFUS].

***Purpuricenus budensis* (Götz, 1783)**

Boboshevo-Simitli Valley: 7 km south of Simitly, 18.07.2001, 10 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]. **Sandanski-Petrich Valley:** Kresna Gorge, the fork for Oshtava Vill., 25.06.2002, 5 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]; Kresna Gorge, Peyo Yavorov Railway Station, 19.07.2002, 1 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]; Sheitan Dere River in Kresna Gorge, 250 m a.s.l., 01.08.2002, 4 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM].

***Purpuricenus kaehleri rossicus* Danilevsky, 2019**

Strandzha Mt.: Marina Reka Protected Area, 5 km north-east of Balgari Vill., 160 m a.s.l., 25-28.06.2003, 1 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]; **Pirin Mt.:** between Gotse Delchev and Katuntsi, 15.07.2004, 3 ex., V. Gashtarov and S. Beshkov leg. [EM].

***Stenhomalus (Obriopsis) bicolor* (Kraatz, 1862)**

Maleshevska Planina Mt.: near Gorna Breznitsa Vill., 41°45'16.07"N, 23°06'32.94"E, 530 m a.s.l., 01.5.2010, 1 ♂, beating from *Crataegus* sp., O. Sivilov & G. Hristov leg. [BFUS].

***Callimoxys gracilis* (Brullé, 1832)**

Sandanski-Petrich Valley: Kresna Gorge, 12.05.1997, 13 ex. collected on flowers of *Rosa spinosa*, V. Gashjarov leg. [VG]. **The Eastern Rhodopes:** Madzharovo, 01-03.05.2003, 6 ex. collected on flowers of *Crataegus* sp., V. Gashjarov leg. [VG].

Lozenska Planina Mt.: 06.06.2003, 28 ex. collected on flowers of Umbrelliferae, V. Gashjtarov leg. [VG].

***Callimus (Callimus) angulatus angulatus* (Schrank, 1789)**

Lyulin Mt.: Dupevitsa Peak, 25.05.2002, 8 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]. **Pirin Mt.:** Sveti Ilia Hill near Kalimantsi Vill., 450-510 m a.s.l., 06.04.-10.05.2002, 6 ex. found in soil traps, M. Langourov leg. [EM]; **Pirin Mt.:** E of Pirin Vill., 41°32'41.00"N, 23°36'14.00"E, 1580 m a.s.l., 14.06.2010, 1 ♀, hand collection, O. Sivilov & B. Zlatkov leg. [BFUS].

***Callimus (Lampropterus) femoratus* (Germar, 1824)**

Pirin Mt.: Katuntsi Vill., 350 m a.s.l., 12.05.2002, 2 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]; SE of Pirin Vill., 41°31'19.20"N, 23°34'42.00"E, 880 m a.s.l., 22.7.2010, 1 ♂, O. Sivilov & B. Zlatkov leg. [BFUS]. **Sandanski-Petrich Valley:** above Novo Konomladi Vill., 1 ex. reared from branch of *Quercus* sp., adult emergence – 14.04.2003, V. Gashtarov leg. [VG].

***Stenopterus flavicornis* Küster, 1846**

The Western Rhodopes: Bachkovo Vill. near Asenovgrad, Bachkovo Monastery, 29.06.2002, 1 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM].

***Stenopterus rufus geniculatus* Kraatz, 1863**

The Western Rhodopes: Yundola Vill. above Velingrad, 20.07.2001, 2 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]. **Lozenska Plnina Mt.:** 1 km SE of Lozen Vill., 42°35'21.90"N, 23°30'44.52"E, 880 m a.s.l., 12.06.2017, 1 ♂, on flowers, D. Gradinarov leg. [BFUS].

LAMIINAE

***Acanthocinus (Acanthocinus) griseus* (Fabricius, 1792)**

Black Sea coast: Lozenets Vill., 30.06.2004, 1 ex. found at light, E. Migliaccio leg. [EM].

***Leiopus (Leiopus) femoratus* Fairmaire, 1859**

Strandzha Mt.: Marina Reka Protected Area, 5 km north-east of Balgari Vill., 160 m a.s.l., 25-28.06.2003, 1 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM].

***Leiopus (Leiopus) linnei* Wallin, Nylander & Kvamme, 2009**

Upper Thracian Plain: Pazardzhik, near the Professional High School in Mechanics and Electrical Engineering, 42°11'52.89"N, 24°19'39.89"E, 210 m a.s.l., 28.05.2008, 1 ♂, D. Kaynarov leg. [BFUS]. **West Balkan Range:** N of Karlukovo Vill., near Prohodna Karst Cave, 43°10'31.00"N, 24°04'21.00"E, 250 m a.s.l., 08.06.2011, 1 ♀, at light, O. Sivilov & B. Zlatkov leg. [BFUS].

***Aegomorphus clavipes* (Schrank, 1781)**

Pirin Mt.: Sveti Ilia Hill near Kalimantsi Vill., 510 m a.s.l., 14.-17.08.2002, 1 ex. found in Malaise trap, M. Langourov leg. [EM].

***Aegomorphus krueperi* (Kraatz, 1859)**

The Eastern Rhodopes: 4 km SE of Madzharovo, 41°35'31.80"N, 25°53'28.80"E, 590 m a.s.l., 03.07.2014, 1 ♂, undergrowth in oak forest, D. Gradinarov leg. [BFUS].

Remark: Second record of the species in Bulgaria (Bringmann, 1997, Migliaccio et al., 2007).

***Agapanthia (Agapanthia) cardui* (Linnaeus, 1767)**

Sandanski-Petrich Valley: 2 km S of Kamenitsa Vill. near Kresna, 170-240 m a.s.l., 09.05.2002, 2 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]. **Strandzha Mt.:** Marina Reka Protected Area, 5 km northeast of Balgari Vill., 160 m a.s.l., 25-28.06.2003, 1 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM].

***Agapanthia (Epopetes) dahli dahli* (C. F. W. Richter, 1821)**

Lyulin Mt.: Dupevitsa Peak, 25.05.2002, 1 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM].

***Agapanthia (Smaragdula) frivaldszkyi* Ganglbauer, 1884**

The Eastern Rhodopes: 1 km NE of Pchelari Vill., 41°38'55.50"N, 25°42'0.43"E, 274 m a.s.l., 27.05.2018, 2 ♂♂, 3 ♀♀, from plants, D. Gradinarov & Y. Petrova leg. [BFUS]. **Remark:** Rare species in Bulgaria (Migliaccio et al., 2007). New record for the Eastern Rhodopes.

***Agapanthia (Smaragdula) violacea* (Fabricius, 1775)**

Sandanski-Petrich Valley: Sandanski, 19.05.1959, 1 ex., M. Witanova leg. [EM]. **Tracian Plane:** Plovdiv Region, 26.04.1961, G. Peshev leg. [EM].

***Agapanthia (Synthapsia) kirbyi kirbyi* (Gyllenhal, 1817)**

Pirin Mt.: Sveti Ilia Hill near Kalimantsi Vill., 450-510 m a.s.l., 10-11.05.2002, 2 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]. **Strandzha Mt.:** Marina Reka Protected Area, 5 km NE of Balgari Vill., 160 m a.s.l., 25-28.06.2003, 1 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]. **Sofia Region:** Sofia City, Darvenitsa residential area, 16.05.2004, 1 ex., E. Kozuharova leg. [EM].

***Agapanthiola leucaspis* (Steven, 1817)**

Strandzha Mt.: Marina Reka Protected Area, 5 km NE of Balgari Vill., 160 m a.s.l., 25-28.06.2003, 2 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM].

***Calamobius filum* (Rossi, 1790)**

Sandanski-Petrich Valley: above Novo Konomladi Vill., 23-24.05.2005, 6 ex., V. Gashtarov leg. [VG]; Novo Konomladi Vill., May 2007, 1 ex., V. Gashtarov leg. [VG].

***Anaesthetis testacea testacea* (Fabricius, 1781)**

Sandanski-Petrich Valley: near Novo Hodzhovo Vill., 41°24'26.58"N, 23°24'25.14"E, 115 m a.s.l., 14.06.2010, 2 ♂♂, at light, O. Sivilov & B. Zlatkov leg. [BFUS]. **Pirin Mt.:** Burovitsa River Valley, 1,5 km SE of Paril Vill., 41°25'57.60"N, 23°42'00.42"E, 755 m a.s.l., 17.06.2013, 1 ex., at light, O. Sivilov & B. Zlatkov leg. [BFUS].

***Deroplia genei genei* (Aragona, 1830)**

The Western Rhodopes: 2 km SW of Asenovgrad, 41°59'34.82"N, 24°50'41.55"E, 740 m a.s.l., 27.4.2017, 1 ♀, at light, O. Sivilov & B. Zlatkov leg. [BFUS]. **Remark:** Rare species in Bulgaria (Migliaccio et al., 2007). New record for the Western Rhodopes.

***Dorcadion (Carinatodorcadion) fulvum erythropterum* Fischer von Waldheim, 1823**

Sofia Region: Chepan Mt., Nova Slivnitsa Vill., 20-24.04.2004, 2 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]. **Middle Pre-Balkan:** Yablanitsa Vill., 01.05.2004, 4 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM].

***Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) equestre transsilvanicum* Ganglbauer, 1884**

Radomir Valley: 1 km E of Belanitsa Vill., 42°28'49.26"N, 22°57'19.02"E, 631 m a.s.l., 05.05.2018, 5 ♂♂, 1 ♀, on the ground, D. Gradinarov & Y. Petrova leg. [BFUS]. **West Balkan Range:** Chepun Mt., 2,5 km NW of Golemo Malovo Vill., 42°57'17.93"N, 22°59'06.63"E, 1078 m a.s.l., 17.05.2019, 2 ♂♂, 1 ♀, on the ground, D. Gradinarov & I. Gjonov leg. [BFUS]. **Remark:** L. Heyrovský reported this subspecies as *Dorcadion equestre* Laxm. a. *niveoconjunctum* Th. Pic. from Dragoman Marsh and from Lyulin Mt. (Heyrovský, 1931). Second record of the subspecies in Bulgaria.

***Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) pedestre pedestre* (Poda von Neuhaus, 1761)**

West Balkan Range: Vrachanski Balkan, Milanovo Vill., 950 m a.s.l., 01.06.2003, 1 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]; Belogradchik, 07.06.2003, 546 m a.s.l., 1 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]. **Maleshevska Planina Mt.:** Gorna Breznitsa Vill., 1400-1500 m a.s.l., 4 ex., T. Ljubomirov leg. [EM]. **Sofia Region:** Dragoman, Dragomansko Blato Lake, 24.04.-06.05.2004, 26 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]. **Middle Pre-Balkan:** Yablanitsa Vill., 01.05.2004, 17 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM].

***Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) tauricum tauricum* Waltl, 1838**

The Eastern Rhodopes: Harmanli, 10.05.1985, 1 ex., Vorisek leg. [EM]. **Sofia Region:** Sofia City, Borisova Gradina Park, 17.05.2002, 2 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]; Chepan Mt., Nova Slivnitsa Vill., 20.04.2004, 2 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]; Dragoman, Dragomansko Blato Lake, 24.04.-06.05.2004, 10 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]. **Middle Pre-Balkan:** Cherven Briag, 01.05.2004, 6 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]. **Lyulin Mt.:** Dupevitsa Peak, 25.05.2002, 1 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM].

***Neodorcadion bilineatum* (Germar, 1824)**

Struma-Petrich Valley: Sandanski, June 1969, 2 ex., Kocourec leg. [EM]; Kozhuh Mt., 08.04.2002, 1 ex., S. Lazarov leg. [EM]; Rupite Vill., 27.04.-03.05.2002, 4 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]; Levunovo Vill., 04.05.2002, 3 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]; 2 km south of Kamenitsa Vill. near Kresna, 170-240 m a.s.l., 09.05.-23.06.2002, 4 ex., E. Migliaccio and M. Langourov leg. [EM]. **Maleshevska Planina Mt.:** Mikrevo Vill., 260 m a.s.l., 05.07.2002, 1 ex., S. Lazarov leg. [EM]. **Pirin Mt.:** Bansko, 29.04.2002, 1 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]; Kalimantsi Vill., 450-510 m a.s.l., 10-11.05.2002, 1 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]; 06.05.2003, 500 m a.s.l., 1 ex., S. Lazarov leg. [EM]; **Slavyanka Mt.:** Katuntsi Vill., 12.05.2002, 2 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM].

***Neodorcadion exornatum* (Frivaldszky von Frivald, 1835)**

The Eastern Rhodopes: Harmanli, 10-20.04.1998, 3 ex., V. Gashtarov leg. [VG]; the same locality, 15.05.1999, 6 ex., V. Gashtarov leg. [VG]; Madzharovo, 20.05.2004, 1 ex., S. Beshkov leg. [VG]. **Tundzha-Sakar Region:** Mezek Vill. near Svilengrad, 06.05.2018, A. Gantchev leg. [VG].

***Exocentrus adpersus* Mulsant, 1846**

Black Sea coast: near Varna, University Botanic Garden, 43°14'06.60"N, 28°00'05.94"E, 55 m a.s.l., 07-16.07.2002, 1 ♀, at light, D. Gradinarov & Y. Petrova leg. [BFUS]; near Aladzha Monastery, W of Zlatni Pyasatsi Resort, 43°16'36.73"N, 28°01'47.56"E, 120 m a.s.l., 26.05.2012, 1 ♀, beating from trees, O. Sivilov & B.

Zlatkov leg. [BFUS]; N of Albena Resort, 43°22'57.07"N, 28°04'21.74"E, 225 m a.s.l., 26.05.2012, 1 ♂, beating from *Quercus* sp. and from *Carpinus* sp., O. Sivilov & B. Zlatkov leg. [BFUS]. **Sandanski-Petrich Valley:** near Novo Hodzhovo Vill., 41°24'26.58"N, 23°24'25.14"E, 115 m a.s.l., 14.06.2010, 1 ♀, at light, O. Sivilov & B. Zlatkov leg. [BFUS]; near Novo Hodzhovo Vill., 41°24'26.00"N, 23°24'27.00"E, 115 m a.s.l., 05.05.2013, 1 ♀, at light, O. Sivilov & B. Zlatkov leg. [BFUS]. **The Eastern Rhodopes:** NE of Madzharovo Vill., bank of Arda River, 41°38'38.21"N, 25°53'37.30"E, 130 m a.s.l., 07.07.2011, 1 ♀, at night with a headlamp, O. Sivilov & B. Zlatkov leg. [BFUS]. **Danubian Plain:** Shumen Heights, 43°15'06.65"N, 26°55'12.97"E, 460 m a.s.l., 18.07.2011, 3 ♀♀, at light, O. Sivilov & B. Zlatkov leg. [BFUS]. **Vlahina Mt.:** Oranovski Prolom Gorge, NW of Zheleznitsa Vill., 41°55'45.18"N, 23°05'21.83"E, 510 m a.s.l., 11.06.2012, 1 ♂, at light, O. Sivilov & B. Zlatkov leg. [BFUS]. **Zemen gorge:** 1 km SW Zemen, 42°28'15.78"N, 22°43'52.86"E, 593 m a.s.l., 18.07.2015, 1 ♂, at light, D. Gradinarov & Y. Petrova leg. [BFUS]. **Pirin Mt.:** above the town of Sandanski, SW of Lilyanovo Vill., 41°36'44.85"N, 23°18'42.90"E, 470 m a.s.l., 27.06.2019, 1 ♂, 1 ♀, at light, O. Sivilov & B. Zlatkov leg. [BFUS]; 1 km NE of Kalimantsi Vill., 41°27'54.13"N, 23°29'19.48"E, 315 m a.s.l., 28.06.2019, 1 ♂, 1 ♀, at light, O. Sivilov & B. Zlatkov leg. [BFUS]; Kresna Gorge, Sheitan Dere River, 41°45'38.07"N, 23°09'16.49"E, 205 m a.s.l., 01.07.2019, 1 ♂, at light, O. Sivilov & B. Zlatkov leg. [BFUS].

***Exocentrus lusitanus* (Linnaeus, 1767)**

Maleshevska Planina Mt.: Kresna Gorge, 41°47'42.50"N, 23°09'27.56"E, 275 m a.s.l., 19.06.2010, 1 ex., beating from *Tilia* sp., O. Sivilov & B. Zlatkov leg. [BFUS]; Kresna Gorge, 41°47'42.67"N, 23°09'27.39"E, 275 m a.s.l., 13.05.2012, 1 ♂, O. Sivilov & B. Zlatkov leg. [BFUS]; Kresna Gorge, 41°47'37.53"N, 23°09'31.90"E, 265 m a.s.l., 07.08.2012, 1 ♂, at light, O. Sivilov & B. Zlatkov leg. [BFUS].

***Exocentrus punctipennis punctipennis* Mulsant & Guillebeau, 1856**

Black Sea Coast: near Varna, University Botanic Garden, 43°14'06.60"N, 28°00'05.94"E, 55 m a.s.l., 07-16.7.2002, 1 ♀, at light, Y. Petrova & D. Gradinarov leg. [BFUS]; near the mouth of Kamchiya River, 42°59'31.56"N, 27°53'14.94"E, 5 m a.s.l., 17.08.2010, 3 ♂♂, 1 ♀, at light, O. Sivilov & B. Zlatkov leg. [BFUS]. **Pirin Mt.:** 1 km NE of Kalimantsi Vill., road to the Belyovo Vill., Sveti Ilia Hill, 41°27'55.20"N, 23°29'31.20"E, 320 m a.s.l., 31.07.2016, 1 ex., at light, Y. Petrova & B. Zlatkov leg. [BFUS].

***Herophila tristis tristis* (Linnaeus, 1767)**

West Balkan Range: Vrachanski Balkan, Vratzata loc. near Vratza, 19.04.2016, 1 ex., V. Gashtarov leg. [VG].

***Lamia textor* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Sandanski-Petrich Valley: Rupite Vill., 27.04.2002, 1 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM].

***Morimus asper funereus* Mulsant, 1862**

Sandanski-Petrich Valley: Kresna, 28.04.2004, 2 ex., V. Beshkov leg. [EM]. **Sofia Region:** Pancharevo Vill., 12.05.2004, K. Nanev leg. [EM]. **West Balkan Range:** Svoge, 600 m a.s.l., 23.05.-16.06.2005, 2 ex., G. Hristova and E. Migliaccio leg. [EM].

***Mesosa (Mesosa) curculionoides* (Linnaeus, 1760)**

Zemen Gorge: near Razhdavitsa Vill., 530 m a.s.l., 21.05.2008, 1 ♂, hand collection, Y. Petrova leg. [BFUS]. **Maleshevska Planina Mt.:** Kresna Gorge, 41°47'37.53"N, 23°09'31.90"E, 265 m a.s.l., 01.05.2013, 1 ♀, on the ground, O. Sivilov & B. Zlatkov leg. [BFUS].

***Monochamus (Monochamus) galloprovincialis pistor* (Germer, 1818)**

West Balkan Range: Svoge, 600 m a.s.l., 31.08.2002, 1 ex., G. Hristova leg. [EM]. **Strandzha Mt.:** Marina Reka Protected Area, 5 km north-east of Balgari Vill., 160 m a.s.l., 25-28.06.2003, 10 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM].

***Monochamus (Monochamus) sutor sutor* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Rila Mt.: Rila Monastery, 1000 m a.s.l., 06.07.2002, 2 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]; Borovets Resort, Yastrebets ski run, 2369 m a.s.l., 14-21.07.2002, 1 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]. **The Western Rhodopes:** between Velingrad and Sarnitsa, 21.07.2001, 1 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM].

***Oberea (Amaurostoma) erythrocephala erythrocephala* (Schrank, 1776)**

Sandanski-Petrich Valley: Sandanski, 03.06.1970, 4 ex., O. Marek leg. [EM]; Kresna, Peyo Yavorov Railway Station, 19.07.2002, 1 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]. **Boboshevo-Simitli Valley:** 7 km south of Simitly, 18.07.2001, 1 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]. **Rila Mt.:** Borovets Resort, 1200 m a.s.l., 26.07.2001, E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]; Rila Monastery, 1100 m a.s.l., 23.06.2002, 1 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM].

***Oberea (Oberea) oculata* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

The Western Rhodopes: Sarnitsa Vill., 21.07.2001, 1 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]; between Dospat and Smolyan, 22.07.2001, 1 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM].

***Oxyilia duponcheli* (Brullé, 1832)**

Sandanski-Petrich Valley: Marikostinovo Vill., Marena place, June 2009, 1 ex. on *Echium italicum* L., V. Gashtarov leg. [VG]; the same place, June 2010, 1 ex. on *Echium italicum* L., V. Gashtarov leg. [VG]. **The Eastern Rhodopes:** 1 km NE of Pchelari Vill., 41°38'55.50"N, 25°42'0.43"E, 274 m a.s.l., 27.05.2018, 1 ♀, on *Echium* sp., D. Gradinarov & Y. Petrova leg. [BFUS]. **Remark:** First record from the Eastern Rhodopes.

***Phytoecia (Coptosia) albovittigera* Heyden, 1863**

Pirin Mt.: 4 km SW of Vlaha Vill., 41°42'59.76"N, 23°11'31.56"E, 263 m a.s.l., 28.04.2018, 2 ♂♂, on Boraginaceae, D. Gradinarov & Y. Petrova leg. [BFUS]. **The Eastern Rhodopes:** 2 km NW of Mandritsa Vill., 41°24'53.70"N, 26°07'23.70"E, 75 m a.s.l., 24.05.2019, 1 ♀, dead on Boraginaceae, D. Gradinarov & Y. Petrova leg. [BFUS]. **Remark:** Rare species in Bulgaria (Migliaccio et al., 2007). New record for Pirin Mts. and for the Eastern Rhodopes.

***Phytoecia (Helladia) praetextata praetextata* (Steven, 1817)**

East Balkan Range: E of Yunets Vill., near Fandakliyska River, 42°55'51.00"N, 27°47'26.00"E, 60 m a.s.l., 24.05.2009, 1 ♀, net sweeping, O. Sivilov leg. [BFUS]. **Remark:** Rare species in Bulgaria (Migliaccio et al., 2007). New record for North-eastern Bulgaria.

***Phytoecia (Musaria) affinis affinis* (Harrer, 1784)**

Rila Mt.: Rila Monastery, 1100 m a.s.l., 23.06.2002, 1 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM].

Sandanski-Petrich Valley: Kresna Gorge, the fork for Oshtava Vill., 25.06.2002, 1 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM].

Phytoecia (Opsilia) coerulescens coerulescens (Scopoli, 1763)

Pirin Mt.: Bansko, between Bunderitsa Chalet and Vihren Peak, 19.07.2001, 1 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]. **Sandanski-Petrich Valley:** Rupite Vill., 27.04.2002, 1 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM].

Phytoecia (Phytoecia) caerulea caerulea (Scopoli, 1772)

Sandanski-Petrich Valley: 2 km south of Kamenitsa Vill. near Kresna, 170–240 m a.s.l., 09.05.2002, 2 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]; Novo Konolmadi Vill., 06.05.2005, 9 ex. collected on *Sinapis* sp., V. Gashtarov leg. [VG].

Phytoecia (Phytoecia) pustulata pustulata (Schrank, 1776)

Lyulin Mt.: Dupevitsa Peak, 25.05.2002, 2 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM].

Phytoecia (Pseudopilemia) hirsutula hirsutula (G. F. Frölich, 1793)

Tracian Plane: Bessaparian Hills near Ognyanovo Vill., 24.04.2000, 1 ex., V. Gashtarov leg. [VG]. **Pirin Mt.:** Sveti Ilia Hill near Kalimantsi Vill., 450–510 m a.s.l., 10–11.05.2002, 1 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]; Kalimanska River, east of Kalimantsi Vill., 12.05.2002, 1 ex., M. Langourov and K. Ivanov leg. [EM].

Pogonocherus (Pogonocherus) hispidus (Linnaeus, 1758)

Black Sea Coast: Balchik, University Botanic Garden, 43°24'20.68"N, 28°08'45.50"E, 35 m a.s.l., 31.05.2019, 1 ♀, in rotten logs, O. Sivilov, B. Zlatkov & R. Beckchiev leg. [BFUS]. **Remark:** Rare species in Bulgaria (Migliaccio et al., 2007). New record for North-eastern Bulgaria.

Pogonocherus (Pityphilus) fasciculatus fasciculatus (De Geer, 1775)

The Western Rhodopes: Grashevo Vill. near Velingrad, 02.05.2002, 1 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM].

Niphona (Niphona) picticornis Mulsant, 1839

Sandanski-Petrich Valley: Volcanic Hill Kozuh near Rupite Vill., 06.07.2008, 1 ex., V. Gashtarov and S. Beshkov leg. [VG]. **Maleshevska Planina Mt.:** Tisata Strict Nature Reserve, 3 km NW of Kresna, 41°44'53.81"N, 23°09'04.09"E, 200 m a.s.l., 01.05.2013, 1 ♀, at light, O. Sivilov & B. Zlatkov leg. [BFUS]. **Remark:** Rare species in Bulgaria (Migliaccio et al., 2007).

Saperda (Lopezcolonia) perforata (Pallas, 1773)

Black Sea Coast: near Varna, University Botanic Garden, 43°14'06.60"N, 28°00'05.94"E, 55 m a.s.l., 07–16.07.2002, 4 ♂♂, 1 ♀, at light, D. Gradinarov & Y. Petrova leg. [BFUS]. **Remark:** Rare species in Bulgaria (Migliaccio et al., 2007). New record for North-eastern Bulgaria.

Saperda (Lopezcolonia) punctata (Linnaeus, 1767)

Black Sea Coast: S of Kranevo Vill., Zlatni Pyasatsi Nature Park, 43°20'02.97"N, 28°03'37.19"E, 160 m a.s.l., 24.07.2011, 1 ♂, at light, O. Sivilov & B. Zlatkov leg. [BFUS]; near the mouth of Kamchiya River, 42°59'31.32"N, 27°53'22.96"E, 1 m a.s.l., 25.07.2011, 1 ♂, 3 ♀♀, at light, O. Sivilov & B. Zlatkov leg. [BFUS]. **Pirin Mt.:**

above Sandanski, SW of Lilyanovo Vill., 41°36'44.85"N, 23°18'42.90"E, 470 m a.s.l., 27.06.2019, 1 ♀, at light, O. Sivilov & B. Zlatkov leg. [BFUS].

***Saperda (Lopezcolonia) scalaris scalaris* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Zemen Gorge: near Zemen, 42°28'13.80"N, 22°43'57.60"E, 590 m a.s.l., 04.07.2009, 1 ♀, hand collection, Y. Petrova leg. [BFUS]. **Pirin Mt.:** SE of Pirin Vill., 41°31'18.27"N, 23°34'41.56"E, 895 m a.s.l., 17.06.2012, 1 ♂, at light, O. Sivilov & B. Zlatkov leg. [BFUS].

***Tetrops praeustus praeustus* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Lyulin Mt.: Dupevitsa Peak, 25.05.2002, 1 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]. **Sofia Region:** Pancharevo Vill., 630 m a.s.l., 02-15.04.2002, 1 ex., M. Langourov leg. [EM]. **Maleshevska Mt.:** Mikrevo Vill., 05.07.2002, 1 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM]. **West Balkan Range:** Vrachanski Balkan, Elenov dol Vill. near Svoge, Sedemte Prestola place, 720 m a.s.l., 14.06.2003, 1 ex., E. Migliaccio leg. [EM].

In this study, localities of 14 rare longhorn taxa were established: *Pedostrangalia (Pedostrangalia) revestita*, *Alocerus moesiacus*, *Anisarthron barbipes*, *Icosium tomentosum atticum*, *Paraclytus sexguttatus*, *Aegomorphus krueperi*, *Agapanthia (Smaragdula) frivaldszkyi*, *Deroplia genei genei*, *Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) equestre transilvanicum*, *Phytoecia (Coptosia) albovittigera*, *Phytoecia (Helladia) praetextata praetextata*, *Pogonocherus (Pogonocherus) hispidus*, *Niphona (Niphona) picticornis*, *Saperda (Lopezcolonia) perforata*. Some of them are extremely rare in Bulgaria. For example, only two localities of *A. krueperi* were previously reported in Bulgaria – Nesebar (Bringmann, 1997) and Razlog (Georgiev, 2020).

Some cerambycid taxa are new regional records: *Callidium violaceum* (West Balkan Range), *Agapanthia (Smaragdula) frivaldszkyi*, *Oxyilia duponcheli*, *Phytoecia (Coptosia) albovittigera* (Eastern Rhodopes), *Deroplia genei genei* (Western Rhodopes), *Niphona (Niphona) picticornis* (Maleshevska Planina Mt.), *Phytoecia (Helladia) praetextata praetextata*, *Pogonocherus (Pogonocherus) hispidus* and *Saperda (Lopezcolonia) perforata* (North-eastern Bulgaria).

In conclusion, the new records enlarge the knowledge about the localities of rare species, as well as the regional distribution of cerambycid taxa in Bulgaria.

Acknowledgements

The authors are grateful to Mikhail Danilevsky (A.N. Severtzov Institute of Ecology and Evolution, Russian Academy of Sciences, Moscow) for the confirmation of *Aegomorphus krueperi* and for the identification of the specimens of *Dorcadion equestre transilvanicum* from the Radomir Valley. We are also grateful to Yana Petrova (National Genetic Laboratory, Sofia, Bulgaria) and Dimitar Kaynarov for kindly providing part of the material.

References

- Bringmann, H.-D. 1997. Die *Morimus* und *Acanthoderes* – Arten Bulgariens (Col., Cerambycidae). – Entomologische Nachrichten und Berichte, 40(4), 237-239.
- Danilevsky, M.L. 2019. Catalogue of Palaearctic Cerambycoidea (Updated: 09.04.2019). <http://www.cerambycidae.net/catalog.pdf>.
- Danilevsky, M.L., D. Gradinarov, O. Sivilov. 2016. A new subspecies of *Morimus verecundus* (Faldermann, 1836) from Bulgaria and a new subspecies of *Morimus asper* (Sulzer, 1776) from Greece (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae). Humanity space. – International almanac, 5(2), 187-191.
- Georgiev, G. 2020. New records of longhorn beetles (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae) in entomological collections in Bulgaria. – Nauka za gorata, 1, 87-99.
- Georgiev, G., Z. Hubenov. 2006. Vertical Distribution and Zoogeographical Characteristics of Cerambycidae (Coleoptera) Family in Bulgaria. – Acta zoologica bulgarica, 58(3), 315-343.
- Georgiev, G., I. Gjonov, V. Sakalian. 2015. New records of longhorn beetles (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae) in Strandzha mountain. – Journal of Entomological Research Society, 17(2), 73-88.
- Heyrovský, L. 1931. Beitrag zur Kenntniss der bulgarischen Cerambyciden. – Mitteilungen aus den Königlichen naturwissenschaftlichen Instituten in Sofia - Bulgarien, 4, 78-86.
- Gradinarov, D., O. Sivilov. 2017. New data and notes on the distribution of *Lioderina linearis* (Hampe, 1870) (Cerambycidae: Callidiini) in Bulgaria. – ZooNotes, 102, 1-4.
- Migliaccio, E., G. Georgiev, V. Gashtarov. 2007. An annotated list of Bulgarian Cerambycids with special view on the rarest species and endemics (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae). Lambillionea, 107(1), Supplément 1, Bruxelles (Tervuren), 78 pp.
- Sabol, O. 2000. Příspěvek k poznání bionomie tesaříka *Lioderina linearis* (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae). – Klapalekiana, 36, 291-296.